

acid (1). This assignment was verified by comparison of and similarity in the spectral data (ir and ms) of its methyl ester (2) with those reported⁵ for the same compound isolated earlier from the plant *Caralluma bucharidii* (family: Asclepiadaceae). It, however, occurred as the methyl ester, and not as the free acid, in the plant.

The seco acid has earlier been reported⁶ from the sediments of a river bed in Indonesia. However, no data whatsoever were reported for the compound. Moreover, the structural assignment was based on identical gc run and similar ms data of its derived methyl ester and a semi-synthetic sample. But it is established that ms data cannot distinguish between the lupane and the hopane series. Also, it was not stated anywhere in the report if the gc conditions employed can distinguish between the two said triterpenoid classes. Our present work, therefore, fully characterises for the first time the seco acid as such from nature and also constitutes the first report of its occurrence in the plant kingdom.

From the non-acidic part of the petrol extract were isolated by preparative tlc lupeol and lupenone, which were identified by comparison (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc, ms) with authentic samples. The co-occurrence of lupenone and the corresponding 3,4-seco acid provides further support to the suggested biogenesis⁶ of the latter by photochemical (or photomimetic) conversion from the corresponding 3-keto precursors.

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Gravimetric Determination of Mercuric Ions by Precipitation with 2-Thioorotic Acid (Amm. Salt)

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2-THIOOROTIC acid (1) has shown a good complexing behaviour with a number of metal ions¹⁻³. It forms a white, stable, sparingly soluble complex, $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_3\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S})_2$. The reaction is quantitative, and the precipitate is filterable after the reaction.

1

Experimental

Solution of ammonium salt of 2-thioorotic acid (Eastman Kodak) (3.44 g) was prepared by heating it with minimum volume of concentrated ammonia solution to obtain a clear solution. Insoluble particles, if any, were removed by filtration. The solution was evaporated nearly to dryness and dried in an oven at 110° for 1 h and then dissolved in distilled water, and made upto 250 ml. A series of mercuric chloride solutions was prepared by weighing 5–400 mg of the compound (AnalaR, 99.5%), and dissolving each in about 25 ml distilled water.

Procedure: To the mercuric salt solution, potassium chloride (AnalaR) (~500 mg) was added, and warmed to 60°. The precipitating solution was added slowly with constant stirring. A white precipitate was formed which settled down in 5–10 min; a few drops of the solution were added further to ensure complete precipitation. The reaction mixture was digested on a water-bath for 30 min. It was then cooled, filtered through a sintered crucible (G-4), and washed with hot water till free from chloride ions (washings tested with AgNO_3 solution). The precipitate was dried at 150° for 1 h in an oven, and weighed. The results have been shown in Table 1.

Effect of diverse ions: Interference, in varying degrees, has been shown by Ag^+ , Hg^+ , Tl^+ , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Rh^{3+} , Pt^{4+} and Cr^{3+} in the experimental conditions of the determination. The removal of these ions, if present, is necessary before applying the above method.

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	Weight of Hg taken g	Weight of Hg-complex obtained g	Weight of Hg calcd. g	Deviation %
1.	0.005 8	0.015 6	0.005 7	-1.70
2.	0.011 5	0.031 0	0.011 4	-0.87
3.	0.019 9	0.054 2	0.020 0	+0.50
4.	0.039 9	0.108 0	0.039 9	0.00
5.	0.059 8	0.162 5	0.060 0	+0.33
6.	0.099 8	0.268 5	0.099 2	-0.60
7.	0.199 6	0.535 4	0.197 9	-0.85
8.	0.199 6	0.535 8	0.198 0	-0.80
9.	0.399 2	1.070 0	0.395 5	-0.92

Results and Discussion

The results obtained for a series of nine determinations (Table 1) have shown that, except in a case where the amount of mercuric ions was as low as 5.8 mg, the experimentally determined values are within $\pm 0.92\%$ deviation in comparison to the true values, suggesting that the method is useful for the gravimetric determination of mercuric ions within 10–400 mg range.

This method is experimentally easier when compared with other gravimetric methods, namely, the sulphide method which requires extraction with CS_2 to ensure the removal of precipitated sulphur, the thionalide method which necessitates an optimum chloride ion concentration⁴, and the periodate method which imposes complete absence of halide ions⁵.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Uranium(VI) using *N-m-Tolyl-p*-methoxybenzohydroxamic Acid

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N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid (TMBHA) has earlier been employed in this laboratory¹⁻⁴ for the solvent extraction of Nb^V,

Ta^V, Ti^{IV}, Mo^{VI} and W^{VI}. All these metals are extracted from highly acidic medium (7–8 *M* HCl) with or without presence of thiocyanate. In continuation of this work, we have used this reagent for the solvent extraction of U^{VI}. The advantage of this method is that U^{VI} is extracted in the pH range 4–6 in contrast to other metals which are generally extracted from highly acidic medium and hence can be separated from these metals. There is no need of adding thiocyanate. The optimum extraction is possible at pH 5.0. Thus U^{VI} can be extracted and separated without any serious interference from most of the metals which are generally associated with it in most of the ores and minerals.

In addition to the extraction behaviour of U^{VI} with TMBHA, we also describe here the preparation and characterisation of the solid metal complex by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements and ir spectra.

Experimental

The stock solution of uranyl nitrate (A.R. grade) was prepared in double-distilled water and standardised⁵. TMBHA was synthesised by the reported method⁶.

A Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements. A Elico pH meter was used for pH measurements. Ir spectra were recorded on a Specord IR-75 at C.I.C., Nagpur. Magnetic measurements were made at room temperature with Gouy balance. Conductance measurements were made using a Toshniwal conductivity meter at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with conventional closed type cell.

Procedure: An aliquot of solution containing about 500 μg of U^{VI} was adjusted to pH 5.0 and the aqueous phase made upto 25 ml. The aqueous phase was shaken for 1 min with 0.025 *M* TMBHA (25 ml) in chloroform. After separation of the two phases, orange-yellow coloured complex was measured spectrophotometrically at 370 nm against reagent blank. The amount of metal extracted was computed from the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The orange-yellow complex absorbs maximum at 370 nm. The Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range of 10–100 μg of U^{VI} per ml of organic solvent. The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity values are $2.5 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.09 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.

The extraction of metal commences at 4.0 pH and is optimum in the pH range 5.0–5.1 beyond which extraction decreases. A 25 ml of 0.025 *M* TMBHA is adequate for the maximum extraction.